

Agricultural Labor Problems of Khelua Development Block in Sibsagar District of Assam.

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ABSTRACT

Sibsagar district is one of the 34 districts of the North East .The districts have been divided into six agro-climatic zones based on physiographic , climate, crops and cropping pattern. In sibsagar district agriculture is the main sector for rural people and this sector contributes the highest amount of GDP and also helps the industrial sector through raw materials .But agricultural production suffers from frequent failure of rains and resulting famines. This makes agricultural production quite uncertain. Therefore their income, living standard ,social status are very poor, population growth ,shrinking of small and cottage industries, demand for informal credit ,agricultural disintegration ,single family and farm credit system are the major problems of agricultural labourers of khelua block in sibsagar district.

Significance of the study

The study on agricultural labour problems of the khelua block is very important.The total population of the district is 11,51,050 out of which 90'43% live in rural areas.Total workforce is 485717 and out of which 25'7% population are agricultural workers and rest of the non agricultural workers are engaged in other activities such as business,shopkeeper.

In Sibsagar district khelua block , agricultural output has fallen due to non availability of farm loans and are not interested in the labourers associated with the agricultural sector.Because of which they are

literally are weak. In Addition women workers are more employed than male labourers engaged in agricultural sector of khelua block and their remuneration is relatively low. These issues require the study of this subject. On the other hand the study helps policy makers to identify their efforts to improve their socio economic condition of the weaker section and particularly of agricultural labour.

Objectives.

- 1/ To study the problems of agricultural laborers of khelua block in sibsagar districts.
- 2/ To provide suggestions to solve the problems of agricultural labour in the khelua block.

Methodology

The present study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data collected from sample village of khelua block of sibsagar district. For this study 40 agricultural labourers from two villages of khelua block have been selected for the total population and 20 agricultural labourers have been taken as the sample of the study. The secondary sources are collected from the book, published and unpublished documents of the district's industrial office of sibsagar, panchayat office website, journals, relevant to the research work.

Problems of agricultural laborers of khelua block in sibsagar district of Assam: While conducting field studies in khelua block of Sibsagar district, 20 agricultural labourers highlighted the problems of agricultural labourers as follows. Below is an analysis of the problems with data.

1/ Disguised unemployment and seasonal unemployment.:

The main problems of farm labourers in sibsagar district khelua block is seasonal unemployment. Because in this region, farmers are engaged in agricultural for six months. For the rest of the year, they are engaged in other non-financial work. As a result their income is low.

2/ Population growth:

Population growth is another problem of agricultural workers. This is because agricultural lands have to be fragmented as a result of the increase in population. As a result there is difficulty in farming with modern methods. As a result the amount of production is low.

3/Climate:

The problem with the agricultural laborers in the khelua block of sibsagar district is that they have to depend on the weather for their farming. on the other hand, due to natural calamities, one cannot be engaged in other agricultural sectors. As a result the amount of income is less than the consumption cost.

4/Another problem faced by the farmers in khelua block is that the wages of women labourers are lower than that of the male labourers and have to contribute more to the agriculture sector. On the other hand the temporary construction of the agricultural sector also creates problems in the field of wages.

5/Lack of local agricultural organisation:

lack of local agricultural organisations is another problem of agricultural workers. This has created problems in terms of fixed wages and fixed employment.

6/The lack of training in ancillary and small enterprise has led to an increase in labour engaged in the agricultural sector and it is a major problem in the agricultural sector. This is because there is a need for training of farmers in rural areas to set up and manage ancillary sectors and small enterprise.

7/The poor people cannot carry out agricultural activities smoothly due to lack of funds. Therefore the rural farmers have to rely on the Go Mohajon, traders commission and the landowners for agricultural activities. poor farmers had no choice but to take loans. At that time formal credit facilities were limited and farmers had to rely on high interest rates offered by the Mohajons. As a result cultivators in a number of some states fail to repay the loans due to low income. Thus borrowed money goes on accumulating which is often called indebtedness.

Sl no	Color	Frequency
1	Disguised unemployment	4
2	Population growth	4
3	Climate	1
4	Wage of woman labour	5
5	Lack of local agriculture	2

	organization	
6	Lack of proper training	2
7	Lack of funds	2

Pie diagram

while discussing the problems of agricultural labourers four of the 20 farm labourers say their main problems are seasonal problems. Because of which the rest of the month of the year has to be unemployed as unemployed in non financial work. population growth is the main problems of agricultural labourers in khelua block as shown in the pie diagram. Agricultural labourers are attracted to non formal credit as the agricultural credit system. As a result , they are forced to take loans at high interest rates. Their debt burden continues to increase .As shown in the figure , 36% of the workers in the khelua blocks are involved in this problem. According to the non resident agricultural labourers in hokhelua block, the remuneration of women farm labourers is lower than that of men. This problem is the main problem of agricultural labourers, according to 5 out of 20 workers or 90%. Instead of modern method of farming the production system is reduced due to the lack of focus on the weather .Which is another problem of agricultural labourers. On the other hand , due to lack of local organisation , there is a problem in fixed remuneration. Due to lack of adequate training system of small scale , agricultural labourers have to remain engaged only in the agricultural sector. As shown in the figure, 10% of

agricultural labourers understand this problem and hold the view that it is one of the major problems of agricultural labourers.

Suggestion for the improvement of agricultural labors:

The following suggestions can be made for the improvement of the socio-economic status of the agricultural laborers in Sibsagar district of Assam.

- 1/ Effective implementation of legislative measures for labor association
- 2/ Resettlement of agricultural workers.
- 3/ Creating alternative sources for seasonal and disguised unemployment.
- 4/ Improving the availability of institutional sources of finance.
- 5/ Proper training for improving the skill of rural agricultural laborers.

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